

Practical Protocols for Improving Safety and Sustainability in Multidisciplinary Research Laboratories

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ABSTRACT: Small and medium-sized multidisciplinary research laboratories often lack specialized systems for chemical safety and sustainability. In many countries, including those with limited or no national regulations for small-scale chemical users, this creates additional challenges for implementing effective safety practices. As a result, chemical inventories are often fragmented and insufficiently managed, increasing safety risks. Additionally, solvents and empty containers are often discarded, despite their potential for recovery and reuse. This article presents a low-cost, user-friendly protocol comprising three complementary components: Shared Chemical Inventory, Solvent Reuse Strategy and Container Repurposing guide designed to improve laboratory safety and sustainability in settings where formal regulations are limited or absent. The protocol was designed for direct accessibility without additional infrastructure or financial investments. Implemented at a medium-sized research institute located in Europe, it achieved an almost 30% reduction in the total chemical waste mass. With its integration in onboarding and simple training modules, the protocol improves safety compliance, reduces cost of virgin solvents, and minimizes chemical waste disposal. Relying on existing laboratory resources demonstrates that principles of responsible chemistry can be effectively applied at the laboratory level without financial investments through voluntary, culturally embraced practices, even in the absence of extensive regulation. Its scalability and adaptability suggest broad relevance for other small- and medium-sized research laboratories, including teaching laboratories and start-ups, contributing to both chemical safety and sustainability goals.

KEYWORDS: laboratory safety, sustainability, chemical inventory, solvent recovery, chemical waste minimization, container reuse, multidisciplinary laboratories

CHEMICAL SAFETY

MULTIDISCIPLINARY
LABORATORIES

1. INTRODUCTION

The global research community increasingly recognizes that laboratory practice must align with broader societal and environmental responsibilities, as reflected in international frameworks such as the 2025 Stockholm Declaration on Chemistry for the Future and the Guiding Principles of Responsible Chemistry developed by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC).^{1,2} The 2025 Stockholm Declaration calls for immediate action to support sustainability and safety in every aspect of scientific work and laboratory practice.¹ To support the sustainable efforts in materials research, the IUPAC has prepared guiding principles of *Responsible Chemistry*.² This framework emphasizes responsibility, safety, sustainability, inclusiveness, ethics, collaboration, equity, integrity, and convergence across disciplines as essential elements of responsible science. Achieving sustainability in research requires progressive improvements in everyday laboratory practices, as increasingly

recognized in recent initiatives promoting sustainable science.^{3,4}

Slovenia's chemical safety framework is primarily governed by the Chemicals Act and associated regulations, which align with European Union directives such as the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) (EC 1907/2006),⁵ and the Classification, Labeling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures (CLP) (EC 1272/2008).⁶ These regulations mandate the safe handling, storage, and disposal of chemicals as well as the classification and labeling of hazardous substances. The Chemicals Office of the Republic of Slovenia oversees compliance through inspections

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and monitoring programs, particularly for entities engaged in the production or testing of chemicals.⁷ This framework operates within the broader European occupational health and safety legislation established under Directive 89/391/EEC,⁸ which mandates employers to assess and prevent workplace risks. Its principles also underpin current approaches to health and safety management in higher education and research organizations.⁹ For research laboratories, Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) is legally required only for nonclinical studies conducted for regulatory submissions. Outside these contexts, academic laboratories may choose to adopt selected GLP principles as internal quality measures, but full GLP compliance is not mandatory and is typically limited to testing facilities formally registered in the national GLP monitoring program.

At the laboratory level, two challenges remain unresolved: (I) chemical waste, particularly solvents and single-use plastics, which dominate the environmental footprint of academic and industrial research facilities,^{10,11} and (II) health and safety risks associated with ineffective chemical management.^{3,12} Inconsistent chemical management is also a well-recognized source of safety risks, particularly when inventories are poorly maintained or unorganized.¹³ Poorly maintained or unorganized chemical inventories often lead to incorrect storage of incompatible substances, accumulation of expired chemicals, and duplicate purchases. When not systematically managed, they become unreliable and increase hazard within the entire research facility.¹⁴ Additionally, a lack of shared chemical inventory results not only in higher waste generation but also in the creation of safety blind spots, particularly when reagents with dual-use potential are overlooked.^{10,13}

Most existing solutions for chemical inventory management are typically designed for chemistry departments or industrial laboratories where trained chemists and safety professionals handle chemical inventories. By contrast, small- and medium-sized multidisciplinary research laboratories often lack such resources. Researchers from diverse fields, such as biology, biotechnology, materials science, civil engineering, agriculture, and forestry, may lack uniform expertise in chemical safety, which becomes a safety concern, particularly when dedicated chemical-safety support is limited or absent. In such environments, advanced digital platforms are expensive and impractical. However, daily use of chemicals still demands clear rules for safety and sustainability.^{3,4,15} While various handbooks and good-practice documents exist, there remains a lack of simple, integrated, and low-cost protocols specifically tailored to the needs of small- and medium-sized multidisciplinary research laboratories. The present work responds to this gap by providing a conscious first-step protocol tailored for small- and medium-scale interdisciplinary laboratories. The protocol consists of three complementary interventions:

1. Shared Chemical Inventory (SCI)—a simplified, standardized system for recording, locating, and managing reagents from purchasing to the end of life.
2. Solvent Reuse Strategy (SRS)—a procedure to recover and reuse common laboratory solvents such as ethanol, isopropanol, and acetone for noncritical applications.
3. Container Repurposing (CR)—a strategy for systematic reuse of intact empty reagent containers for secondary purposes.

Each component addresses safety, sustainability, and compliance, while requiring no specialized software and

minimal resources. Importantly, the protocol was designed for simplicity and transferability, enabling implementation by nonchemists in interdisciplinary laboratories.

2. LABORATORY CONTEXT

The presented protocol was developed at the InnoRenew CoE (Slovenia), a small-scale multidisciplinary research institute (employing 42 researchers), affiliated with the University of Primorska. Three laboratories routinely operate chemical reagents: Characterization Laboratory (CHL), Engineered Living Materials Laboratory (ELM), and Composite Laboratory (CL). These units support research in wood technology, materials science, biobased materials, and engineered living materials.

Laboratory users include undergraduate/graduate students, doctoral candidates, postdoctoral researchers, technicians, and short-term visitors (e.g., traineeships/internships). They represent diverse disciplines such as biology, biotechnology, wood science, civil engineering, and forestry, and most of them do not have specialized training in chemical safety. This interdisciplinary environment shaped the design of the presented protocol, focusing on standardized chemical management and simplified sustainability measures that are accessible to all laboratory users.

The laboratories are equipped with fire-safety storage cabinets compliant with DIN EN 14470-1, fume hoods, and a rotary evaporator (Rotavapor R-300, BÜCHI, Switzerland) suitable for solvent recovery. Before this work, approximately 450 different substances were in use, stored under appropriate conditions inconsistently but managed across laboratories. At this scale, the absence of a shared inventory system led to duplicate purchases and an unnecessary accumulation of chemical waste. The following protocol was developed and implemented to harmonize the inventory across all laboratories, improve safety, and enable simple sustainability measures.

Prior to this work, chemical management was primarily decentralized with each laboratory maintaining its own records. While storage cabinets and fume hoods ensured baseline compliance with European standards (REACH, CLP, and national waste regulations), the absence of a unified chemical inventory created inefficiencies and risks. For instance, solvent waste represented approximately 45% of the annual chemical disposal mass, and duplicate purchases accounted for nearly 15–20% of acquisitions in common chemicals, such as ethanol and acetone. Expired chemicals and inconsistently labeled containers further increased safety risks, particularly for visiting researchers with a limited familiarity with local practices. Importantly, the institute operates without a dedicated chemical safety officer, relying instead on shared training and the initiative of laboratory staff. These constraints mirror those faced by many small- and medium-sized academic and applied research institutes, reinforcing the need for scalable, low-cost protocols to improve both safety and sustainability.

3. PROTOCOL OVERVIEW

The protocol is organized into three complementary procedures, each presented in a standardized format. Together, these measures strengthen safety and align with principles of green and responsible chemistry (e.g., minimizing waste, reducing hazardous substances, improving resource efficiency, and embedding safety, ethics, and sustainability into daily laboratory practice)^{2,16} and support more sustainable labo-

ratory operations while requiring minimal financial investment and expertise.

3.1. Shared Chemical Inventory (SCI)

Purpose. To establish a unified, simple in use, accessible inventory system, that increases laboratory safety, improves chemical storage, reduces duplicate purchases, and enhances collaboration across users.

Materials/Setup.

- Fire-safety cabinets with location coding: LAB-Cabinet_Shelf, e.g., *CHL-1.1*, *ELM-2.3*
Shelf arrangement: front-to-back columns with columns ordered from left to right (Figure 1)
- Labels with storage codes
- Cloud spreadsheet (e.g., Excel/SharePoint)
- Safety Data Sheets (SDSs) and the Technical Rules for Hazardous Substances (TRGS510)¹⁷

Figure 1. Standardized coding and storage system. (A) Fire-safety cabinet with shelf codes. (B) Shelf arrangement example. (C) Schematic representation of front-to-back and left-to-right shelf arrangement.

Procedure.

- Assign responsibility—designate technicians or responsible persons to coordinate inventory setup.
- Catalogue chemicals—record all existing chemicals (including partial containers) into the inventory file.
- Segregate stock—relocate incompatible chemicals according to storage classes (SDS section 7.2) and SDS guidance.
- Populate fields—enter all necessary information regarding identification and navigation, usage, safety and end of life using SDS and container labels (Figure 2).
- Upload to shared platform—assign read-only access to most users and editing rights to designated responsible persons.
- Maintain entries—update when new chemicals are purchased, containers are emptied, and quantities changed.

Safety Considerations. Classification and segregation followed the Technical Rules for Hazardous Substances (TRGS510—storage classes) and SDS guidance. To minimize

Figure 2. Overview of chemical inventory fields grouped into navigation, usage control, safety, and end-of-life categories.

the hazard, physically separate incompatible materials. Use appropriate PPE while handling the chemicals to minimize the risk of unintended exposure.

Recordkeeping. Chemical inventory serves as a shared, continuously, and systematically updated record of all chemicals in use, supporting safe handling, audits, and regulatory reporting. New entries, chemical usage, and emptied containers are routinely recorded by designated persons. The inventory is checked annually to monitor procurement and actual use of chemicals.

Training. Operation and rules are presented to all laboratory users and are accessible together with SCI via a shared platform. Brief onboarding is for all new users. Reminder leaflets were placed on cabinets illustrating proper chemical arrangement

Transferability. Excel-based SCI requires no specialized software. The coding system, shelf arrangements, and field categories can be directly applied in multidisciplinary institutions. A ready-to-use Excel template of the Shared Chemical Inventory (SCI) is provided as [Supporting Information](#) to facilitate adoption in other laboratories.

3.2. Solvent Reuse Strategy (SRS)

Purpose. To reduce flammable liquid waste and solvent purchases by recovering ethanol, isopropanol, and acetone for reuse in noncritical applications (cleaning, rinsing).

Materials/Setup.

- Glass collection trays, solvents recovery bottles, filter paper.
- Position trays at sinks/benches; decant to clearly labeled recovery bottles.
- Rotary evaporator with water bath, vacuum pump, vertical condenser, and recirculating chiller.
- Screw-cap storage bottles labeled, e.g., *Recovered Solvent—noncritical application*.
- PPE: nitrile gloves, splash goggles, lab coat.

The basic setup and workflow used for solvent recovery are illustrated in Figure 3.

Procedure.

Figure 3. Solvent recovery workflow: (A) Rotary evaporator setup, (B) collection tray and recovery bottle, and (C) simplified flow scheme.

- Collect used solvents in labeled recovery bottles from glassware rinsing or experimental procedures (collect each solvent separately or together—depends on generated waste and application).
- Prefilter if particulates are visible in the recovery bottle. Conduct filtration in a fume hood to a clean intermediate container.
- Distill under reduced pressure until 90% of recovery (following the evaporation sequence determined by solvent boiling points).
- Store recovered solvent in labeled screw-cap bottles in a flammables cabinet, segregated from virgin stock; reuse for surface cleaning, preliminary glassware rinsing, and wipe-downs.

A complete overview of the solvent recovery workflow, including collection, prefiltration, distillation, and storage for reuse, is shown in Figure 4.

Safety Considerations. Exclude solvents contaminated with toxic, reactive, or persistent chemicals (e.g., heavy metals and strong oxidizers). Always operate in a fume hood; confirm seals and coolant flow while using the rotary evaporator; and never distill to dryness. Use appropriate PPE while operating the chemicals.

Recordkeeping. Record volumes of recovered solvents per month as a part of sustainability monitoring. Perform the procedure monthly or on demand after collecting some volume (e.g., 2 L).

Training. The operation is presented to all laboratory users and is accessible via a shared platform. Brief onboarding for all new users, including solvent collection, appropriate use, and exclusion criteria. Training on distillation was provided to designated technicians.

Transferability. Required standard rotary evaporator infrastructure is available in most research laboratories. Small facilities without equipment could partner with neighboring laboratories for solvent recovery.

3.3. Containers Repurposing (CR)

Purpose. To reduce plastic waste and procurement demand, reusing intact, clean, compatible chemical bottles for secondary tasks (e.g., waste segregation, sample transport, hood debris jars).

Figure 4. Solvent recovery workflow with collection, prefiltration, distillation, and storage/reuse stages.

Materials/Setup.

- Shared chemical inventory.
- Rinse water or compatible cleaning solvent; drying rack.
- New adhesive labels for relabeling.
- Separate storage area for repurposed containers.

Procedure.

- Select containers—identify intact HDPE, PP, or glass bottles previously holding low- or moderate-hazard substances.
- Exclude containers with acutely toxic residues and/or structural damage.
- Verify that both the container and its cap are intact and provide a proper seal to prevent leakage or contamination.
- Clean empty containers and caps with water or an appropriate solvent and dry completely.
- Remove or deface the original label and apply the new label, stating the intended reuse.
- Store prepared containers separately from virgin stored containers to avoid confusion.
- Repurpose containers, e.g., for waste segregation, sample transport, storage, fume hood debris collection, or another application.

The overall workflow for eligibility assessment, preparation, and repurposing is summarized in Figure 5.

Safety Considerations. Exclude containers previously holding acutely toxic or highly reactive substances. Consult SCI and SDS for safe operation. Before repurposing, verify the structural integrity. Ensure the container is suitable for its new purpose and never use it for food or drink.

Recordkeeping. Track the amount of repurposed containers to monitor the reduction in laboratory waste generation and procurement of new bottles as part of sustainability monitoring.

Training. Laboratory users are trained to identify eligible and excluded containers.

Transferability. Applicable in any laboratory. Requires no specialized equipment.

Figure 5. Summary of the container repurposing protocol, outlining eligibility, preparation, and repurposing steps.

4. IMPACT OF THE PROTOCOL

To evaluate the effectiveness of the protocol, the waste profile of the laboratories was analyzed after implementation and compared with a modeled baseline scenario without intervention. Because the evaluation focused on outcomes that could be reliably measured within a single semiannual monitoring cycle, the study did not include a systematic assessment of safety-risk mitigation or long-term behavioral changes among early career researchers. These aspects are expected to emerge over longer implementation periods and represent important areas for future evaluation.

4.1. Waste Profile without Intervention

Before implementation of the protocol, chemical waste was dominated by nonhalogenated organic solvents (~45% of total waste mass), inorganic residues (~21%), and empty containers (~15%). Oils accounted for ~9%, while acids, bases, and halogenated solvents combined contributed ~10% (Figure 6A). This distribution is consistent with literature reports identifying solvents and consumables as dominant contributors to laboratory waste streams.^{11,12}

4.2. Effect of Protocol Implementation

Following the implemented protocol, approximately 30% of the total chemical waste mass was saved from disposal (Figure 6B). Solvent recovery brought the largest contribution of around 25% to the overall reduction in total chemical waste, primarily from the nonhalogenated solvent fraction. Container repurposing achieved an additional 5% reduction primarily by proper categorization and reducing the number of bottles sent for disposal. These measures lowered both the volume of hazardous waste requiring disposal and the purchase of virgin solvents and new containers. The shared inventory further reduced waste indirectly by preventing duplicate purchases and limiting the accumulation of expired reagents.

The obtained results were achieved using existing laboratory infrastructure and direct operational practices without additional investments. The data in Figure 6 represent the total chemical waste generated by all laboratories of the institute over one semiannual monitoring cycle (6 months).

5. DISCUSSION

Meaningful improvements in laboratory safety and sustainability can be achieved even through low-cost, accessible interventions. The presented protocol is easy to implement by nonchemists in multidisciplinary settings. It provides step-by-step guidance for chemical safety and a first step toward sustainability monitoring within laboratories. By decreasing the volume of flammable liquid waste, lowering the need for purchasing new solvents and containers, and limiting duplicate purchases, the protocol reduced the environmental impact. At the same time, the protocol supports more consistent safety practices and encourages reagent sharing within the laboratory culture.

Because the protocol relies only on standard laboratory infrastructure (rotary evaporator, fume hood, and storage cabinets) and simple procedures, it can be readily implemented in other academic or industrial laboratories, including those with limited or no national regulations for small-scale chemical users. The protocol was intentionally designed for multidisciplinary research settings, including environments where users may not have advanced chemistry training and therefore emphasizes simplicity, clarity, and reliance on standard

Figure 6. Effect of the implemented protocol on chemical waste generation. (A) Projected waste profile without intervention. (B) Measured waste profile with intervention. Yellow bars represent the fractions recovered or repurposed under the implemented protocol (~30% of total). Insets show relative contributions of waste categories (% of total). The data represent the total chemical waste generated by all laboratories of the institute over one semiannual monitoring cycle (6 months).

laboratory infrastructure. It combines safety compliance (segregation, storage, inventory control) with sustainability goals (waste reduction, reuse, chemicals sharing). Brief onboarding and periodic refreshers are sufficient to ensure consistent protocol adoption. For storage classification, the internationally recognized standard TRGS510 (Germany) was adopted, acknowledging easy application even by non-specialists. The shared inventory supports hazard communication and clustering requirements. Solvent recovery and container repurposing reduce the volume of hazardous materials for disposal. This aligns with European regulatory frameworks and standards (EU CLP hazard classification, REACH requirements, TRGS510 principles) and supports responsible chemistry principles promoted by IUPAC. Beyond practical outcomes, the protocol also contributes to building a culture of responsibility by embedding safety and sustainability into daily routines. Although this aspect was not evaluated during the initial implementation, integrating such practices into routine laboratory work is expected to support safety awareness and responsible chemical use among undergraduate and graduate students. Introducing simple and structured procedures early in training has the potential to strengthen long-term safety and sustainability practices among early career researchers.

The primary limitation is reliance on access to a rotary evaporator for solvent recovery. However, this equipment is common in most laboratories and could be accessed through interinstitutional collaborations. The protocol described here was intentionally designed as a low-complexity and resource-efficient approach that can be implemented using standard laboratory equipment and simple digital tools (such as spreadsheet-based inventories). It provides an accessible first step toward more structured chemical management in laboratories with limited organizational or technical resources. By emphasizing early stage hazard prevention, reduced chemical exposure, and more efficient resource use, the protocol is consistent with the underlying principles of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approach.¹⁸ It provides an accessible first step that supports laboratories with limited technical or organizational capacity in moving toward more systematic safety and sustainability practices. Broader adoption of such low-cost, scalable protocols could contribute to global sustainability targets. By reducing solvent waste, avoiding duplicate purchases, and improving hazard communication, these practices directly support the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Future opportunities include linking chemical inventory with neighboring institutions, creating reagent sharing networks, and integrating solvent recovery metrics into sustainability reporting. Lightweight digital tools such as QR-based labels or shared cloud spreadsheets could enhance tracking without undermining accessibility.¹⁹ Furthermore, establishing metrics for solvent reuse volumes, avoided costs, and CO₂-equivalent reductions would enable benchmarking across institutions and strengthen reporting for institutional sustainability strategies. In this way, the presented protocol translates the principle of responsible chemistry into a daily laboratory practice by uniting safety, sustainability, and accessibility.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a practical, low-cost protocol for improving chemical safety and sustainability in multidisciplinary research laboratories. By combination of a shared chemical inventory, solvent recovery, and container repurposing, this approach reduces chemical waste, prevents unnecessary procurement, and improves compliance with safety standards. Importantly, the protocol was developed for accessibility by nonchemists, ensuring applicability beyond chemistry-focused facilities. By integrating safety, sustainability, and accessibility, the presented approach demonstrates how responsible chemistry principles can be embedded in laboratory operations without major infrastructure investments.

Beyond the immediate waste-reduction and compliance benefits observed, the protocol was also designed to support long-term improvements in laboratory culture by introducing early career researchers to sustainable and safe chemical practices. Although these broader cultural effects were not evaluated in this initial implementation, the protocol's simplicity and reliance on existing infrastructure make it potentially adaptable to diverse research environments, including teaching laboratories, small start-ups, and institutions with limited resources. Broader implementation could cumulatively advance institutional sustainability reporting, align with international safety frameworks, and contribute to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.chas.5c00163>.

Ready-to-use Excel template for the Shared Chemical Inventory (XLSX)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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